

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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EFFICIENT USE OF RESOURCES IN THE PRODUCTION PROCESS USING THE EXAMPLE OF COTTON AND TEXTILE CLUSTERS

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Abstract: The ever-increasing demands on products and new types of fabrics from government orders and industry actualize a variety of approaches to regulating and optimizing the parameters of the production cycle, maintaining a sufficient level of profitability. One of the effective management technologies is the process approach. Its advantages are visibility, transparency, regulation of labor functions and accurate resource provision. The combination of economic, technological and market parameters in the assessment of decisions made regarding the range change and improvement of existing products will have a positive effect on the quality of planning and final results, will contribute to the stability of the material, technical and resource base. In general, this approach is aimed at achieving relative economic independence and project-based (order-based) payback for the activities of textile industry enterprises.

Key words: textile production, management, process approach, process modeling, order, profitability, innovation, assortment.

Annotatsiya: Davlat buyurtmalari va sanoat tomonidan mahsulotlarga va yangi turdagi matolarga bo'lgan doimiy ortib borayotgan talab ishlab chiqarish siklining parametrlarini tartibga solish va optimallashtirish, rentabellikning yetarli darajasini saqlab qolish uchun turli xil yondashuvlarni dolzarblashtiradi. Samarali boshqaruv texnologiyalaridan biri bu jarayon yondashuvidir. Uning afzalliklari - ko'rinish, shaffoflik, mehnat funksiyalarini tartibga solish va resurslarni aniq ta'minlash. Mavjud mahsulotlar assortimentini o'zgartirish va takomillashtirish bo'yicha qabul qilingan qarorlarni baholashda iqtisodiy, texnologik va bozor parametrlarining uyg'unligi rejalashtirish sifati va yakuniy natijalarga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi, moddiy-texnikaviy va resurs bazasining barqarorligiga yordam beradi. Umuman olganda, bu yondashuv to'qimachilik sanoati korxonalari faoliyatining nisbiy iqtisodiy mustaqilligi va loyiha (buyurtma asosida) qoplanishiga erishishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: to'qimachilik ishlab chiqarish, boshqaruv, jarayon yondashuvi, jarayonni modellashtirish, tartib, rentabellik, innovatsiya, assortiment.

Аннотация: Постоянно растущие требования к продукции и новым видам тканей со стороны государственных заказов и промышленности актуализируют разнообразные подходы к регулированию и оптимизации параметров производственного цикла, поддержанию достаточного уровня рентабельности. Одной из эффективных технологий управления является процессный подход. Его преимуществами являются наглядность, прозрачность, регламентация трудовых функций и точное ресурсное обеспечение. Сочетание экономических, технологических и рыночных параметров при оценке принимаемых решений по изменению ассортимента и совершенствованию существующих изделий положительно скажется на качестве планирования и конечных результатах, будет способствовать стабильности материально-технической и ресурсной базы. В целом данный подход направлен на достижение относительной экономической самостоятельности и проектной (заказной) окупаемости деятельности предприятий текстильной промышленности.

Ключевые слова: текстильное производство, управление, процессный подход, процессное моделирование, заказ, рентабельность, инновации, ассортимент.

INTRODUCTION

The management of the textile industry is aimed at solving a number of problems, the overcoming of which will contribute to the growth of economic indicators of production both in individual regions and at the national level. The need to update the material base is one of the urgent tasks, since the deterioration of equipment and its obsolescence make it difficult to introduce innovative methods, create new types of fabrics, which generally leads to a loss of market share and a decrease in consumer interest. The result of the management and control of fixed assets and equipment is a project payback, reduced downtime and repair costs. The rationalization of business processes in the textile industry contributes to increasing the effects of decisions taken aimed at developing the competitive potential of enterprises, reducing non-production losses, and increasing liquidity. The increase in competitive advantages is associated with the innovative activity of textile enterprises, which is significantly constrained by regulatory restrictions, low attractiveness and high risks for investors, but at the same time, small and medium-sized businesses in the industry can significantly improve their market positions due to flexibility, cost control during economic crises and relatively small investments (as a rule, own financial resources).

One of the main factors influencing the efficiency of the garment and textile industries is the inclusion of enterprises in production and distribution chains, in which consumer demand is a guideline that determines the stability of work in the chosen direction, cyclical supply and payback.

The continuation of this aspect of optimizing the production cycle and access to resources and sales markets has been received in scientific papers devoted to intelligent technologies for managing a closed production cycle using raw materials and waste based on crowdsourcing. The introduction of digital technologies and solutions into the production, management and functional processes of textile industry enterprises creates a huge potential for economic and market efficiency due to:

- optimizing the production rhythm, reducing equipment downtime and increasing its throughput;
- integration of technical, economic and resource data to make informed decisions;
- development of operational flexibility of production through early recognition of promising global consumption trends and formation of unique competencies of management specialists and key functional staff.

LITERATURE REVIEW OF THE TOPIC

The creation of cotton-textile clusters in Uzbekistan will present a chance to quickly penetrate the global textile market and completely meet domestic demand, beginning with the production of deep-processed finished textile products and ending with the cultivation of raw cotton. Rural areas will also see the creation of contemporary employment opportunities and a significant improvement in living standards as a result of population growth.

The following directions are among the experiences gathered in the establishment of clusters in foreign nations and their practice:

The first approach is thought to be the Italian model (industrial districts), which is predicated on internal clusters that function as a formal or informal community to enter and occupy the market and a high concentration of small businesses for export expansion.

Industrial clusters, which create concentric circles (centralized organizations) with a central management structure, are thought to represent the second path. Higher education institutions, scientific research facilities, and scientific laboratories are examples of such industrial clusters. The experiences of Germany, France, South Korea, Japan, and South Korea all show this cluster development. They have well-established official internal links as well as strong collaborations for outside markets.

This cluster creation strategy is characterized by the dispersion of inventive activity and the absence of linear connections. The key to guaranteeing mutual integration is giving each cluster member a chain link to the system's control hardware. Relying on additional financial resources during the cluster's establishment creates a requirement for state intervention and motivates it to take on the role of primary financial supplier.

Although the state's backing and ample financial resources are the weak points in its organization, this cluster formation approach is thought to be the primary tool or strategy for boosting the nation's competitiveness in the global market.

The third direction is said to be typical of the industrialization era; the United States, Scandinavia, and Switzerland were major users of these clustering techniques. The triple helix model of clustering places a greater emphasis on innovation creation, with the primary goal being to sustain competitiveness by disseminating the innovations made across cluster members.

Robert Kaplan and David Norton's research led to the conclusion that, among other things, at least four factors finance, buyers, internal business processes, and development should be taken into consideration when creating a system of harmonized indicators of successfully operating enterprises.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a variety of research methodologies, including comparative analysis, statistical data analysis, economic comparison and analysis, logical reasoning, scientific abstraction, analysis and synthesis, and inductive and deductive reasoning.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Textile industry enterprises operate in difficult economic conditions, which give the processes of production adaptation a virtually continuous character. Management systems must adapt to external challenges caused by the competitive environment, growing consumer demands for product quality and characteristics, and innovative technologies.

The management functions in the textile industry have some special features:

- order orientation is gaining more and more influence on planning, calculation and analytical substantiation of new types of products, their implementation, purchase of equipment, as risks are significantly reduced and profitability can be influenced;

- The regulation of production processes is based on a system of specific regulations and technological maps that facilitate cost control and compliance with labor standards that prevent significant cost overruns and running costs;

- a clear link between control and planning, the purpose of which is the continuous improvement of technological, economic and personnel parameters of the production cycle.

In the scientific literature, experts pay attention to the process approach, noting the following advantages of its application in management:

- regulation and formalization of procedures, allowing to identify reserves, vulnerabilities at the operational level of production, accurate resource provision;

- a roadmap for the actions of specialists and coordination of the functions of various departments, clarifying the official powers and status of employees;

- the optimal ratio of automated and manual labor, methods of monitoring the results;

- accumulation of competencies and preservation of the production model in case of changes in the economic situation of the market, change of owners or managers of the business;

- transparency of operations and functions, which positively affects the quality of the main and intermediate results.

Business process design is a technology for organizing production, carried out taking into account the compliance of the internal potential (resources, personnel, equipment) with the strategy of the enterprise, which allows to establish a range of profitability variations and parameters of its regulation, including possible risks. The main risks are personnel, technological and market risks related to consumer demand and its dynamism. Scientific papers contain more extensive classifications of risks of industry enterprises caused by external factors and internal vulnerabilities that influence the choice of strategy and preventive response measures.

The process model is a simplified roadmap for the production of textile products, which highlights the main four stages, each of which ends with a specific result and allows you to move on to the next stage. Direct and reverse processes can be distinguished here. The straight lines (blue arrows in Fig. 1) allow planning, production and sales to be carried out while achieving positive planned intermediate and final results (Fig.1).

Figure 1. Process model of a simplified roadmap for textile production.

The presented processes begin with planning the technological, ergonomic, physico-chemical and economic parameters of fabric production. Drawing up technological maps and planning the assortment, improving the characteristics of manufactured fabrics or the production of new products should answer the question of achieving the required level of profitability in accordance with the order received, the possibility of establishing long-term relationships with customers, expanding sales, and stable demand.

The dotted arrows in Figure 1 indicate some of the possible outcomes in accordance with the step-by-step implementation of direct processes and possible vulnerabilities that can be studied and analyzed to make corrective management decisions.

Reverse processes (red arrows in Fig. 1) ensure the quality of production cycle control and create conditions for systematic analytical work on the study of the competitive environment, resources, technologies and consumer expectations.

Taking into account the analysis of literary sources, it is advisable to clarify the advantages of using the process approach (Fig. 2).

One of the key advantages is the adaptation of the management and production system to the requirements of consumers (Fig.2).

Figure 2. Adaptation of the management and production system to the requirements of consumers.

The textile market has a high degree of diversification and is updated annually due to scientific and technological progress, the needs of technical enterprises and niche demand from government customers. The company's management should not only cooperate with suppliers and loyal consumers, but also study industry production trends in interconnected industries, participate in projects, and develop cluster-network partnerships, including institutions of science, education, and the expert community.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS.

The process technology of management of textile industry enterprises has the following advantages in the current conditions:

- allows you to improve the quality of production process planning, including market and supplier analysis, study of analogues of products, raw materials, evaluation of possible supply and reservation options, preparatory work for each order;
- strengthens the regulation of the functions and status of employees, including the calculation and analytical justification of labor standards, time, technologies required in the production of the planned product range, eliminates unnecessary operations, increases operational flexibility and productivity;
- improves the quality of feedback for the management staff in order to make the right corrective decisions and eliminate problems caused by technological, product range or market changes;
- improves the effectiveness of investment and credit policy due to the transparency of operations and cash flows, a sufficient level of profitability;

- optimizes the financial and economic performance of the textile enterprise, promotes the growth of turnover, profits and the rational formation of the asset structure.

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